

al examination of pollen grains stained with I-KI solution. Percent seed set under self-pollination was evaluated by bagging the main panicles of the hybrid plants.

The pollinators were classified as: effective restorers, where fertility resto-

ration was above 80%; weak restorers or integrades where fertility restoration was 20-80%; and maintainers (nonrestorers) where fertility restoration was less than 10% (see table).

The effective restorers are being used

to produce F_1 hybrids for evaluating heterosis and combining ability. A recurrent backcross that uses maintainers to transfer the genome into wild aborted (WA) cytoplasm for developing additional cms stocks is in progress. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

IET6148, a variety for direct seeding

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Very early-maturing rice varieties were evaluated for direct seeding as part of the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement

Project Uniform Variety Trial I. Seed was soaked for 12 h and broadcast in puddled, leveled soil at 110 kg/ha. Water was carefully controlled for 1 week and then the crop was regularly irrigated. Trials were conducted in both kharif and rabi.

Cauvery and Tellahamsa, a popular short-duration high yielding variety, were checks. IET6148, 6149, 5860, 6155, 5858,4106,4107, and 6233 have been

evaluated since 1979 kharif.

IET6148, a progeny of Bala/Co 13, developed at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, gave consistently high (5.8 t/ha) yields. During 1979 kharif IET6148 was superior to all entries and yielded 6.2 t/ha. In 1980 kharif and 1981 rabi it yielded 5.9 and 6.1 t/ha, equal with Tellahamsa. ET6148 flowers in 75 days and has short bold grain. □

Govind, an early-maturing rice variety

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Govind, an early-maturing variety developed from the cross IR20/IR24, was recently released in Uttar Pradesh for general cultivation. Govind is a semidwarf (90 cm) variety that can be direct-seeded in rainfed fields or transplanted. It has 95- to 109-day maturity when direct-seeded in rainfed fields and 105-110 days when transplanted. Grains are long, slender, and translucent with good cooking quality and intermediate amylose content (23%).

Govind has been tested throughout Uttar Pradesh and in All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) trials for 5 years. Its performance in the AICRIP uniform variety trials is given in Table 1. Performance in the upland direct-seeded standard varietal trials and station trials (transplanting) is given in Tables 2 and 3.

Govind resists bacterial leaf blight, leaf blast, and brown leaf spot diseases and is moderately resistant to planthop-

Table 1. Performance of Govind in AICRIP trials when direct-seeded in upland rainfed fields.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Average	Days to 50% flowering (1980)
	1979 (mean of 23 locations)	1980 (mean of 31 locations)	1981 (mean of 17 locations)		
Govind	3.3	3.4	3.1	3.3	75
Bala	3.2	—	—	3.2	—
Cauvery	2.9	2.8	2.3	2.7	74
Akashi	—	2.8	—	2.8	69
Local check	3.4	3.3	2.5	3.1	75

Table 2. Performance of Govind in standard varietal trials in U.P. when direct-seeded in upland rainfed field.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Average	Days to maturity (1981)
	1980 (mean of 7 locations)	1981 (mean of 6 locations)			
Govind	2.1	2.5		2.3	96
Cauvery	2.1 ^a	2.0		2.1	98
N22	1.4	1.8		1.6	87

^a 5 locations only.

Table 3. Performance of Govind in U.P. when transplanted in station trials.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Average	Days to 50% flowering (1980)
	1979 (mean of 6 locations)	1980 (mean of 9 locations)			
Govind	5.1	3.9		4.5	81
Saket 4	5.1	4.4		4.7	87